

Using "Masnaviyi Manavi" Stories to Improve Students' Critical Thinking

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Abstract:

At the same time, the policy of education and upbringing demands a new social order. Currently, our society requires people who can quickly rebuild and find a way out of a difficult situation by creating ideas. Deep changes taking place in modern education put the use of new technologies of education and training as a priority. Teachers have the opportunity to choose the teaching methods and technologies that, in their opinion, are the most optimal for building and designing the educational process.

Keywords: critical thinking, pedagogical technology, education, stories, ability.

The purpose of the technology of development of critical thinking is to develop mental abilities of students, which are necessary not only for studying, but also for later life (ability to make clear decisions, work with information, analyze different aspects of events), etc. The formation of critical thinking skills in students depends on the organization of classes by professors and teachers of higher education using educational technologies and creating favorable conditions for their independent education. Today, our pedagogues and parents are required not only to pay special attention to the education of young people, but also to talk with them more and at the same time encourage our young people to think critically. In this regard, several reforms are being implemented in the field of education in our country. The science of pedagogy has always been looking for ways to achieve high results in the educational process and has been constantly improving its tools, methods and forms. There was a desire to find some method or a set of methods that would allow the achievement of the intended goal. As a result, we can see that different methodologies have emerged. With the accumulation of pedagogical experience, new, more effective methods began to be created. In teaching practice, various ways, methods and forms of teaching are widely used. However, the search for a single effective (integral) approach to teaching

is still being continued. The search for didactic approaches and didactic tools that can turn teaching into a unique production technological process continues.

The development of critical thinking in students and young people implies the formation of basic relationships with a varied, independent, conscious point of view towards oneself and the world. This kind of perspective ensures that learning is authentic - because it is truly conscious and reflexive, and expands the individual's communicative capacities. Critical thinking is a special type of thinking that creates conclusions by analyzing evidence. This concept is complex and has many different definitions, including rationality, skepticism, objective analysis, and evidence testing. Critical thinking is a form of thinking that is self-directed, self-disciplined, self-controlled, and self-correcting. Its prerequisite is to agree to strict standards of consciousness improvement and to apply them with vigilance. Critical thinking requires the acquisition of effective communication and problem-solving skills, as well as overcoming our inherent egocentrism and sociocentrism. The mechanism of critical thinking includes mental operations that determine the process of discernment and evidence: setting goals, defining problems, introducing hypotheses, introducing arguments, justifying them, predicting consequences, accepting or not accepting an alternative point of view. Includes the ability to apply basic intellectual skills (knowledge and understanding) to synthesize, analyze, and evaluate complex and ambiguous situations and problems. This is identifying problems, clarifying the situation, analyzing the evidence, studying the problem in depth, developing criteria for evaluating the decisions and reliability of information sources, and avoiding generalizations. Relying on the latest concepts aimed at the development of critical thinking, we believe that the following intellectual skills play an important role in its development: assessment of the reliability of the information source; the ability to separate the necessary information and the ability to redevelop it; analyze and evaluate assumptions, conclusions, citations, assumptions and plausible views; the ability to ask questions to obtain or verify more accurate information; comparing and defining the problem according to different worldviews, different approaches and points of view; to be precise in expressing one's point of view, to be able to choose the right language; to be able to make a decision and justify the correctness of one's choice. In order to use the mentioned skills in everyday life and professional activities, students need to have certain knowledge and experiences. On this basis, it is possible to develop complex programs of preparation for professional activity based on the development of critical thinking in students, which determines the problem of our research work. It is known that the task of the speaker is never limited to presenting a certain amount of information. As a rule, the speaker is obliged to defend his point of view, convince him that it is right, etc. This is one of the main job duties of a speaker. Based on the generalization of the experiences of the advanced countries of the world, it will be possible to form a new social culture among young people, to help them to correctly define their paths based on the principles of development, not to repeat the mistakes of the past, and to learn the necessary lessons from them. From this point of view, it is important for pedagogues to have the ability to speak. Their further improvement, expansion and increase in efficiency is one of the urgent issues of the day. Jalaluddin Rumi's work "Masnaviyi Manavi" has been the cause of various disputes and debates among Western and Eastern scholars for seven centuries. The fact that Rumi is classified as a poet of humanity by world thinkers, and his work "Masnavi" is evaluated as a book after the Qur'an, an encyclopedia of mysticism, a sea of spirituality or a book of the world, is a proof of the value and influence of this work. A poetic and commentary translation of Masnavi has also been published. Rumi's poetry is the highest peak of Eastern poetry. Experts say that there are few poets in the West who, like Rumi, researched the human heart, expressed the human psyche, and the spiritual strength of a person in poetry. you first of all build trust in the person. And Rumi reveals the divinity of man in a very profound way. The sun of Rumi's poetry - Ishq. If it is necessary to unite people around one truth or one Love, then Rumi's poetry can amalgamate this work. We say that in order to be a perfect person, you need to know Sufism, you need to know

religion, you need to know philosophy, history, etc. Rumi synthesized all these in his work. Rumi's poetry frees a person from delusions, superficialities, shallowness, and various limitations. Therefore, it is as much modern poetry as it is historical poetry.

Jalaluddin Rumi's "Spiritual Masnavi", which is considered one of the greatest monuments of world culture, consists of 6 notebooks, more precisely, 54 thousand verses, and it was written by Maulana in 10 years.

So, what is expressed in Rumi's "Masnavi" that, even after more than seven centuries, the discussions and discussions about it are still unfinished? They say that he said: "Masnaviyi mo dokoni ast wahdat, gairi wahid harchi bini on bat ast." For example, "Our Masnavi is a shop of unity, if you see anything other than unity in this shop, then you know that it is idolatry. So there is nothing but unity in this store. That is, "Masnavi" thoroughly develops and explores the issues of the unity of God and faith. No matter which narration he refers to, it comes down to the idea of unity. In his opinion, the core issue of "Masnavi" is the issue of faith," says poet Askar Mahkam.

There are schools of spiritual studies in many countries of the world, including Iran, Turkey, Pakistan and India. It is said that even in the territory of Uzbekistan, before the Shura revolution, the study of spirituality was widely developed, and this book of Rumi was preserved in every scholarly household, like the holy book after the Qur'an. Poet and translator Askar Mahkam believes that no one has interpreted Masnavi better than the Uzbek poet Boborahim Mashrab.

CONCLUSION

The content of the work is a treasure that reexamines not only the students, but also the minds of all mankind. Even in terms of education, it is one of the most important tasks to inculcate the work in the minds of young children and, as a result, to raise a successful generation.

Based on the above, we can say that each student creates an integrated cognitive field that combines all available theoretical knowledge, practical information, skills and abilities. If a student thinks critically, he can easily enter any stage of the lesson. Each stage has its own methodological methods aimed at completing tasks. By combining them, the teacher can plan lessons according to the maturity level of the students, the purpose of the lesson and the amount of learning material. Each method and strategy of critical thinking is aimed at bringing out the creative potential of students. That is why it is important to organize the lesson based on modern educational technologies.

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